

CO₂ conversion to solar fuels and chemicals: opening the new paths

Gabriele Centi and Claudio Ampelli

*Department ChiBioFarAm – University of Messina, ERIC aisbl and CASPE/INSTM, V.le F. Stagno
d'Alcontres 31, 98166 Messina, Italy*

* Corresponding authors: centi@unime.it, ampellic@unime.it

Abstract

This future article discusses the new prospects and directions of CO₂ conversion via the photo-electro-catalytic (PEC) route. Second (2nd) generation solar fuels and chemicals (SFs) are generated directly in PEC systems without forming molecular H₂ as an intermediate, overcoming the thermodynamics limitations and practical issues encountered for electro-fuels produced by H₂ from water electrolysis. A distributed and decentralised production of SFs requires very compact, highly integrated and intensified technologies. Among the existing reactors of advanced design (based on artificial leaves or photosynthesis), the integrated photovoltaic plus electrocatalytic (PV-EC) device is the only system (demonstrated at large scale) to produce SFs with high solar-to-fuel (STF) efficiencies. However, while the literature indicates STF efficiency as the main (and only) measure of process performance, we remark here the need to refer to productivity (in terms of current density) and make tests with reliable flow PEC systems (with electrodes of at least 5-10 cm²) to accelerate the scaling-up process. Many limitations exist in PEC systems, but most can be overcome by proper electrode and cell engineering, thus going beyond the electrocatalysts' properties. Furthermore, we present the development of artificial leaf (tree) devices for green H₂ production to meet the challenge of a low-carbon future with distributed production of chemicals and energy carriers, providing new ideas and research directions from a personal perspective.

Keywords

Solar fuels, artificial leaf, PEC devices, PV-EC devices, cell engineering, H₂, chemicals from the air.

Introduction

The conversion of CO₂ in electrocatalytic devices driven by renewable energy (i.e. sunlight) is a topic of growing scientific and technological interest to meet important challenges such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions and improving carbon circularity and resilience [1-4]. The term solar fuels or chemicals (SFs) does not involve the production of molecular H₂ as an intermediate, thus different from the conventional thermocatalytic processes to convert CO₂ into chemicals or fuels (e-fuels or electrofuels) using H₂ produced by electrolysis [5-8].

Although e-fuel processes are at a higher level of technological development, SF technologies have several advantages: i) avoiding the formation of a high-energy intermediate (H₂) to produce lower-energy molecules (e.g. methanol), with an intrinsic limit in the energy efficiency of the process (in electrocatalytic routes, the conversion of CO₂ occurs via protons/electrons, without forming H₂), ii) avoiding the thermodynamic limitations related to catalytic reactions involving molecular H₂, and iii) allowing the development of compact and integrated devices that directly use solar energy overcoming the many issues (both environmental and of renewable energy management) related to electrolyzers for H₂ production. SF technologies are thus crucial to achieve higher efficiencies at lower costs to produce fuels or chemicals using solar energy. For these reasons, we have emphasised the need to go beyond the 1st generation of e-fuel technologies and directly develop the 2nd generation of SF technologies [5, 9-11].

Although the concept of SFs involves the novel trio of photo-, electro- and plasma catalysis [12] and their combinations (also with microbial processes), we focus here the discussion on (photo)electro-catalysis, being the area that currently presents the best prospects for faster implementation [11]. Furthermore, H₂ production is the focus of most literature studies claiming to produce SFs or using technologies for their production, such as those based on artificial leaves (AL) or photosynthesis devices [13]. However, the target of these devices is to produce the final products directly (in a single stage) using solar energy. Therefore, they should be developed for converting CO₂ or N₂, as we early introduced [14]. Similarly, in CO₂ conversion, the target should be a product with final direct utilisation rather than a product like CO that requires further conversion, typically by (complex) thermocatalytic technologies such as the Fischer-Tropsch process. In addition, SF technologies should be applied for distributed (decentralised) production, requiring very compact, highly integrated and intensified technologies, which are not compatible with multistep processes with operations under very different conditions (near ambient conditions in photo-electro-conversion of CO₂ and high temperature and pressure for thermocatalytic routes). In other words, we argued in several early papers [15-17] that, taking the challenge of SF and AL devices, it is necessary to address the issue of complexity rather than choosing simpler reactions and devices

because they allow a higher solar-to-fuel (STF) or Faradaic efficiency (FE). Creating the basis for future sustainable chemical production requires to meet this challenge [18, 19].

At the same time, the development of solar fuels/chemical technologies opens a large series of innovative transformations in the chemical and energy storage sector that can disruptively transform the area, pushing an economy based on renewables [18, 19]. However, accelerating this transformation would require a broader-minded and more visionary approach than currently used. Despite several thousand papers and reviews on electrocatalysis in the last few years, most of them focused on a restricted range of applications, approaches and conditions of uses without exploring new routes and the novel possibilities offered by electrocatalysis.

This contribution aims to discuss some case examples, taken from our activities in line with the aims of "future articles", to remark on the need to enlarge the current approaches and explore new frontier possibilities. At the same time, it is necessary to go beyond the current approaches in designing and understanding electrocatalysts.

The role of photoelectrochemical devices engineering

While the literature mainly focuses on electrocatalysts and aspects such as controlling nanomorphology and other similar features, we remarked that performance (under conditions relevant to upscaling results) depends on electrode and reactor design [20]. CO₂ conversion can be made in advanced reactor designs with reduced energy losses to maximise STF conversion [20, 21]. A common classification divides these systems into i) photoelectrochemical and ii) integrated photovoltaic plus electrocatalytic (PV/EC) devices [13]. The photoelectrochemical approach involves the development of a visible light-enabled photoelectrode able to auto-generate the voltage needed for the reaction. On the contrary, in PV/EC reactors, an electrolyser is integrated with an external solar cell (photovoltaic or perovskite cell) that powers the electrochemical process [22]. In both systems, an ion exchange membrane physically separates the cathodic and anodic processes but introduces additional costs and transport resistances. These could be avoided by using an approach that leads to forming the same products on both the cathode and anode sides. Within the EU DECADE project (DistributEd Chemicals And fuels production from CO₂ in photoelectrocatalytic DEvices, project 862030), we are developing a cell where bioethanol is oxidised at the anode to form ethyl acetate (EA), and at the cathode CO₂ is reduced to acetate which reacts with bioethanol to form EA. The product is a mixture of bioethanol and EA (plus ethyl formate as a byproduct), which can be used directly as a green solvent or fuel additive, avoiding the often high costs for downstream processing of the photoelectrocatalytic devices. Cells are part of a process and must be designed to account for upstream and downstream processing, often the

determining element in the overall cost. We emphasised the need for a proper design to facilitate product recovery, indicating, for example, the need for "gas-phase" (or electrolyte-less) operations for CO₂ reduction (by using gas-diffusion layer - GDL - electrodes) [17, 23, 24]. This approach is now popular, called zero-gap electrolyzers [20, 25, 26]. We first reported that this approach dramatically changes the CO₂ coverage at the surface, enabling the production of long-chain carbon products in CO₂ electroreduction [27]. CO₂ coverage, rather than characteristics of the electrocatalyst (as typically investigated in the literature), is the factor determining the possibility of obtaining >C₁ products in CO₂ electroreduction [17, 23, 28].

Thus, cell and electrode engineering, rather than studying (only) the electrocatalyst, is the key to controlling performance and selectivity in CO₂ electro-conversion. In terms of developing devices that integrate the direct use of solar energy (a key to designing artificial-tree devices independent of externalities, e.g. renewable energy supply, and thus designing sustainable and resilient devices), the integrated PV/EC approach is currently the only way to achieve high STF efficiencies [13] and the only one demonstrated on a large scale [29]. Note that, as discussed more in-depth elsewhere [13], the literature reports only STF efficiencies as a performance measure. However, without reporting a result on the productivity, such as the current density, and without making tests with reliable flow photoelectrocatalytic reactors with electrodes larger than a minimum size (around 5-10 cm²), the reliability of the STF efficiencies is limited.

Following this philosophy from our earlier devices [30, 31], we recently developed a high-performance PV/EC cell able to convert CO₂ with high SFT efficiency (up to 10%) along with high current densities using electrodes based only on earth-abundant materials [32].

Looking at the future

While the performance and understanding of these devices should be further improved (a push factor), there is the need to identify the pulling elements to drive the future of SF and AL devices. They determine the needs and characteristics for the use and the fundamental aspects to be developed. In the DECADE mentioned above project, a limiting factor is the lack of information on electrocatalysis in a nearly alcoholic medium, which was revealed to be quite different from that in an aqueous medium. Almost all studies are limited to aqueous electrolytes or a few different media (such as ionic liquid), greatly limiting the range of applications of these devices.

As part of another EU project (EPOCH, Electrocatalytic Production of liquid Organic hydrogen carrier and CHEmicals from lignin, project 101070976), we are investigating the coupling in an electrochemical cell of the regeneration (by cathodic hydrogenation) of liquid Organic hydrogen carrier (LOHC) with the anodic oxidation of lignin or its derivatives to produce high-value chemicals.

Substituting the commonly used oxygen evolution reaction (OER), typically employing noble metal electrocatalysts, with other anodic oxidation reactions would reduce process costs by producing valuable chemicals, improve kinetics and efficiency at the anode, and create market synergies between biorefinery and H₂ economy (via lowering costs for hydrogen carriers). However, results on the design of efficient anodes for converting lignin or its derivatives are very lacking in the literature. Other examples were given in a recent review [9].

It is also necessary to design new solutions that overcome current limitations. A limit in the green H₂ economy is the cost dependence and great impact on CO₂ emissions of electrolyzers using the current energy mix [33]. Photoelectrochemical distributed production would offer new possibilities to overcome these limitations, but it has the shortcomings of H₂ storage. Therefore, the target is to develop PV/EC devices that integrate the storage of H₂ to enable continuous (even overnight) or on-demand H₂ production. Using the previously cited results on high-performance PV/EC cells able to convert CO₂ into formate and H₂, formate/formic acid can temporarily store H₂, allowing (by its controlled catalytic decomposition) to produce H₂ on demand (or during the night) and also recycling CO₂. This concept, illustrated in Figure 1, allows the development of artificial trees for distributed production of H₂. We are developing a pilot unit to demonstrate the feasibility of this concept.

Figure 1. Concept of artificial trees for a distributed H₂ production. The PV/EC cell inset is reproduced with permission from ref [32], RCS Copyright 2023.

Furthermore, we are also exploring the possibility of a step further by (i) integrating functionalised membranes, allowing the direct capture of CO₂ and H₂O from the air, (ii) converting them to acetate in a PV/EC device (an extension of previous studies on the electro-conversion of CO₂ into acetate

[34]), and (iii) using acetate as the feed for microbial conversion into food components (carbohydrates, proteins, etc.) [35]. Alternatively, capturing N₂ to produce fertilisers (ammonium nitrate or urea) from the air in a direct PV/EC device is an extension of the studies on electrocatalytic reduction of N₂ + H₂O to ammonia [36-39].

In parallel, pushing the frontiers of photoelectrocatalytic devices also requires the development of new fundamental approaches to understanding electrocatalysis. Current approaches, mainly mediated by heterogeneous catalysis, fail to provide a solid generalised theory for the design of electrocatalysis [10, 40] and, in general, photo or plasma catalysts. We are developing a new approach, combining theory and experiments, based on selective energy transfer via localised surface phonons and their interaction with charges and localised electrical fields generated by applying a potential [41].

Conclusions

Photo-electro-catalysis is a crucial technology for CO₂ conversion into solar fuels and chemicals and developing artificial leaf (tree) devices to meet the challenge of a low-carbon future with distributed production of chemicals and energy carriers. However, it would be necessary to tune and broaden the current approaches to i) aspects to focus on, ii) fields of application and implications of cell engineering, and iii) fundamental understanding of the mechanisms and crucial elements to design the electrocatalysts. This "future article" provides some clues to move forward, focusing on our ideas and research directions.

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